

Random Number Generators Survey

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Abstract—The use of random numbers is essential in randomized algorithms, and many statistical methods are using them on random sampling, this is due to the fact that examining all the possible cases is unpractical. Nowadays, the most common used of random numbers is in simulation studies of stochastic processes. In fact, the security of many cryptographic systems relies on the generating of random numbers. However, cryptographic applications require random numbers with different criteria than those used in simulation. This study investigates pseudo-random numbers PRN, Quasi-random numbers QRN, and cryptographic random numbers CRN. The survey goal is to cover several random number generators and examining their statistic proprietaries using several testing algorithms.

Index Terms—Pseudo-random numbers PRN, Quasi-random numbers QRN, Pseudo-random number generators PRNG

I. INTRODUCTION

Generating a truly random bit needs a natural source of randomness. Using such source in designing hardware devices or software programs to generate random sequence is difficult. Also, these random bit generators can be affected by external factors and malfunction [1]. Hardware random bit generators are based on a natural source occurs in some physical phenomena such as: thermal noise from a semiconductor diode or resistor provides truly unpredictable random numbers, and most of the true random number generators are hardware plugged to a computer.

On the other hand, software random bit generators could be based on the system clock, elapsed time between keystrokes, mouse movement, or buffers content. The behavior of these processes depends on many aspects including the computer platform. The output of such generator may be biased or correlated; biased means the probability of the source producing a 1 is not equal to 1/2, where correlated means the probability of the source producing a 1 depends on previous bits that have been produced. There are many techniques, such as de-skewing, that could be used to generate truly random bit sequences from the output bits of insufficient generators [1].

Digital computers cannot generate truly random numbers; in fact it is inconvenient to plug external hardware on com-

puters as a source of randomness. Therefore, pseudo-random numbers are used instead; these numbers mimic the properties of random numbers and drawn from uniform distribution. Uniform distribution on finite set of numbers is one in which each possible number is equally probable. A sequence of random numbers must satisfy two statistical properties: uniformity and independence. Cryptographic applications requirements for randomness are much more strict than other applications, unpredictability is an essential condition in randomness; it means that we cannot predict the next digit by knowing the previous one. This leads to the concept of a one-way function [2][3].

II. PSEUDORANDOM NUMBER GENERATOR ALGORITHMS

Pseudo-random Number Generators (PRNG) are deterministic algorithms used to generate sequences that pass many tests of randomness. Most pseudo-random generators use recursion to produce sequences of numbers that appears to be random. Such generators yield number recursively. The next number in the sequences is determined by the previous one. The recurrences start with a value called the seed, and each time a recurrence starts with the same seed, the same sequence is produced. The length of a sequence before it gets repeated is the period or the cycle length.

$$x_{n+1} = ax_n + b \quad (\text{mod } N) \quad (1)$$

The parameters a, b and N determine the characteristics of the random number generator. A good pseudorandom number generator should satisfy the following properties

- 1) Uniformity: the generated sequence should be distributed uniformly on $(0, 1)$
- 2) Independence: the generated sequence should not be correlated with each other
- 3) Cryptographically secure
- 4) Replication: the sequence should be reducible
- 5) Period length: the period should be long enough before numbers gets repeated
- 6) Speed and memory usage: the generator should be fast and not require a lot of storage
- 7) Cost per bit should be moderate (not in cryptographic applications) [4]

A. Midsquare Method

In 1946, John von Neumann used computer's arithmetic operation to generate random numbers. The basic idea is to start with a n -digit number called the seed x_0 , and square it to get $2n$ digits (to have $2n$ -digit add necessary number of zeros to the left of X), then take the middle n digits to obtain the next n -digit number x_1 ; then square x_1 and take the middle n -digits again and so on. We place the decimal point at the left of each x_i to make it uniformly distributed $[0,1]$. Table 1 demonstrates the Mid-square Method using 1234 as initial seed.

Table I: Sample random numbers using mid square method

Case	N four digit	n^2
1	1234	1522756
2	0.5227	27321529
3	0.3215	10336225
4	0.3362	11303044
5	0.3030	9180900

The method suffers from the short period, and whenever zero appears in the sequence, it continually perpetuates itself. For example: when $x_0 = 2100$, we get the sequence 0.2100, 0.4100, 0.8100, 0.6100, 0.2100, 0.4100, and after four numbers the sequence starts to repeat itself. Once zero is detected, we could restart the middle-square method on a new start value, however we can not avoid long cycles. Metropolis worked with 38-bit numbers and obtained a sequence of 750,000 numbers before the sequence degenerated to zero, and the resulting 750,000 numbers of 38 bits passed statistical test for randomness.

B. Linear Congruential Generators

In 1948, D. H. Lehmer proposed a simple generator using a linear recurrence on a finite set.

Definition II.1. let $a, b, x_0 \in \mathbb{Z}m$. The linear congruential generator (LCG) with parameter $M, a, b,$ and x_0 defines a sequence x_n in $\mathbb{Z}M$

$$x_n = a.x_{n-1} + b \quad \text{mod } M$$

where $n > 0$ And y_n is a pseudorandom sequence in $(0,1)$ where $y_n = x_n/M$.

a is called the multiplier, b is the increment, and M is the modulus of the generator. Often, the increment b is set to be zero, and the generator in this case is called linear Multiplicative Congruential Generator (LMCG).

The quality of PRG depends on the choice for the parameter $a, b,$ and M , tables have been published that specify a proper choice of these parameters see [5]. In choosing the modulus, we want M to be large, since the period cannot have more than m elements. Also, we want to choose M in such a way that speed up the computation of $(a.x_{n-1} + b) \text{ mod } M$. Computing $y \text{ mod } m$ requires division operation, but if we pick m to be word size w , particularly $2n$, then the addition

operation gives modulo w . Therefore, the typical values being used are $M = 2^{32}$, or Mersenne prime $M = 2^{31} - 1$, and in high-precision calculations $M = 248$ is used. The longest possible period of the linear congruential generator is M in case of $b \neq 0$, and $M - 1$ in case of $b = 0$.

A linear congruential generator has a full period of length m if and only if :

- b is relatively prime to M . i.e. the only positive integer that divides both m and b is 1 ($\text{gcd}(b, M) = 1$).
- $a \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$ for every p dividing M i.e. if p is a prime number that divides M , then p divides $b = a - 1$
- $a \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ whenever 4 divides M . i.e. if 4 divides M , then 4 divides $b = a - 1$.

All these conditions are met if $m = 2^k$ for some integer k, b is an odd integer, and $a = 4c + 1$ for some integer c . Linear congruential generator is predictable and insecure for cryptographic purposes.

Several modifications have been proposed to improve the linear congruential generator. One approach is to replace the simple recurrence with an arbitrary function and the PRNG is called general first order congruential generator [6], in this method, the congruential generator modulo m is obtained by first order (one step) recursion:

$y_{n+1} \equiv f(y_n) \pmod{m}, n = 0, 1, \dots$ where f is an integer-valued function on $\mathbb{Z}M$, in practice, f and the initial value y_0 are chosen in such a way that the sequence y_0, y_1, \dots is periodic and $\text{per}(y_n)$ is large. When we derive a uniform sequence $x_n = y_n/m$, we get $\text{per}(x_n) = \text{per}(y_n)$ and we can get $\text{per}(y_n) = m$ by starting from periodic sequence y_0, y_1, \dots with $\text{per}(y_n) = m$ and defining $f(y_n) = y_{n+1}$ where $0 \leq n \leq m - 1$.

Quadratic congruential generator proposed by Knuth, he uses a polynomial of degree two for the recurrence and power of two as the modulus:

$x_i \equiv (dx_{i-1}^2 + ax_{i-1} + c) \pmod{m}$, the maximum length period of the quadratic generator is m , the advantage of using higher degree polynomials is not clear [2].

Another variation of LCG proposed by MacLaren and Marsaglia in 1965, the method involves shuffling the output stream; this shuffling could increase the period [3]. Bays and Durham use a single generator to fill a table of length k and then select number from the table to fill up the table by using a single stream

Bays and Durham's shuffling Algorithm

- 1) Initialize the table T with x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k ,
 $i = 1$, generate x_{k+i} and set $y_i = x_{k+i}$
 - 2) Generate j from y_i (use mod k)
 - 3) Set $i = i + 1$
 - 4) Set $y_i = T(j)$
 - 5) Generate x_{k+i} And refresh $T(j)$ with x_{k+i}
-

For example, using the generator with $m=31$, $a=3$, and $x_0=9$, we get the sequence 27, 19, 26, 16, 17, 20, 29, 25, 13, 8, 24, 10, 30, 28, 22, 4, 12, 5, 15, 14, 11, 2, 6, 18, 23, 7, 21, 1, 3, 9, we select k to be 8 and initialize the table as 27, 19, 26, 16, 17, 20, 29, 25, then use the next number 13 as the first value in the output stream and also to form random index into the table. If we form the index as $13 \bmod 8+1$ we get the sixth value in the table 20, as the second number in the output stream. We generate the next number in the original stream 8, and put it in the table, so the table have now 27, 19, 26, 16, 17, 8, 29, 25. Now, we use 20 as index to the table and get the fifth value in the table 17, as the third number in the output stream.

C. lagged-Fibonacci Generators

A simple Fibonacci sequence has $x_{i+2} = x_{i+1} + x_i$, we can generalize this recurrence by combining two apart elements instead of two consecutive elements. The Additive Lagged-Fibonacci Generator is given by the following recurrence:

$$x_n = x_{n-j} + x_{n-k} \pmod{m} \quad k > j \quad (2)$$

The performance of Additive Lagged-Fibonacci Generator depends on the parameters j , k , and m . If m is a prime number and $k > j$ then the period can be as large as $m^k - 1$. If the modulus is a power of 2, say 2^p , then the longest possible period is $(2^k - 1)2^{p-1}$; and has $2^{(k-1) \times (p-1)}$ different full-period cycles.

Lagged-Fibonacci Generator is cheap to compute and it does well on standard statistical tests. It may require an initial seed sequence rather than a single number for the seed, and the care must be taken in selecting the initial seed sequence, if we do so, the output of the Lagged-Fibonacci Generator has better randomness properties than the congruential generators [3]. The Generator can be parameterized through its initial values, since it has a magnificent number of different cycles. The Multiplicative Lagged-Fibonacci Generator is defined by:

$$x_n = x_{n-j} \times x_{n-k} \pmod{2^m} \quad k > j \quad (3)$$

The maximal-period of the generator is $(2^k - 1)2^{m-3}$, which is a quarter the Additive Lagged-Fibonacci Generator's period length.

D. Shift Register Generators

Shift register generator (SRG) is consisting of shift registers and exclusive-OR gates. Let p , a small prime (usually $p = 2$), let $k \geq 2$ be an integer, generate a k -step linear recurring sequence $y_0, y_1, \dots \in Z_p$ by :

$$y_{n+k} \equiv \sum_{l=0}^{k-1} a_l y_{n+l} \pmod{2} \quad (4)$$

for $n = 0, 1, \dots$, where y_0, y_1, \dots, y_{k-1} are initial values that all not all zero. The integer coefficients a_0, \dots, a_{k-1} are chosen as they are from primitive polynomial over F_p in form $f(x) = x^k - \sum_{l=0}^{k-1} a_l x^l$. The period of $(y_n) = p^k - 1$.

There are two techniques to transform the sequence y_0, y_1, \dots produced by the recurrence (4) into a pseudorandom sequence in $[0,1]$ they are called digital multi-step method and the generalized feedback shift register (GFSR). In digital multi-step method, the sequence y_0, y_1, \dots is transformed into a sequence x_0, x_1, \dots of uniform PRN in the following way, we choose an integer m with $2 \leq m \leq k$ and put

$$x_n = \sum_{j=1}^m y_{mn+j-1} p^{(-j)} \quad (5)$$

for $n = 0, 1, \dots$. In other word, the number x_n are obtained by splitting the sequence y_0, y_1, \dots into consecutive blocks of length m and then interpreting each block as a digital expansion in base p of a number in $[0,1)$

The generalized feedback shift register was suggested by Lewis and Payne in 1973 [7]. Let $m \geq 2$ and integers $h_1, \dots, h_m \geq 0$, and we put

$$x_n = \sum_{j=1}^m y_{n+h_j} p^{-j} \quad (6)$$

for $n = 0, 1, \dots$. The numbers x_n belong to $[0,1)$ and are called GFSR pseudorandom numbers. The period of $x_n = p^k - 1$. GFSR is implemented based on the vectors $Y_n = (y_{n+h_1}, \dots, y_{n+h_m})$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots$. It follows from equation (4) that Y_n can be generated by the vector recursion $Y_{n+k} \equiv \sum_{l=0}^{k-1} a_l Y_{n+l} \pmod{p}$ for $n = 0, 1, \dots$ and if Y_n is interpreted as a block of digits in base p , then we obtain x_n due to equation (6). The generalized feedback shift register (GFSR) generator is widely used since the algorithm generation is very fast and the sequence has a long period that is independent of the word size of the machine, however, this algorithm has several limitations [8].

Twisted GFSR generator (TGFSR) is the same as the GFSR generator, but it is based on the linear recurrence $x_{l+n} = x_{l+m} \oplus x_l A$ for $l = 0, 1, \dots$, where A is a $w \times w$ matrix with 0-1 components, and each x_l is a row vector over finite field of 2. While the GFSR is based on the recurrence $x_{l+n} = x_{l+m} \oplus x_l$ of the primitive polynomial of form $1 + x^n + x^m$.

Generalized Feedback Shift Register Algorithm

Let $x[n]$ be an array of n integers of word size and l be an integer variable. The GFSR algorithm is described as follows:

- 1) $l \leftarrow 0$.
 - 2) Set $x[0], x[1], \dots, x[n-1]$ to some initial values.
 - 3) Output $x[l]$.
 - 4) $x[l] \leftarrow x[(l+m) \bmod n] \oplus x[l]$
 - 5) $l \leftarrow (l+1) \bmod n$
 - 6) Goto Step 3.
-

The algorithm of TGFSR is obtained by replacing Step 4 in the above algorithm with

$$x[l] \leftarrow x[(l+m) \bmod n] \oplus \text{shiftRight}(x[l]) \oplus \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if LSB of } x[l]=0 \\ a & \text{if LSB of } x[l]=1 \end{cases}$$

where a is a fixed constant word and shift means the one-bit shift operation [8].

E. Combined Generators

In order to have sequences with good statistical properties and longer periods, methods of combining two or more generators are suggested.

Considering two random sequences y_n and z_n , let say that y_n was produced using Shift Register generator, where z_n was produced using Additive lagged-Fibonacci, then the combined sequence w_n is

$$w_n = y_n + z_n \pmod{p} \quad (7)$$

The Period of w_n is the least common multiple of the periods of y_n and z_n . In 1982, Wichmann and Hill suggested combining three different multiplicative LCGs with different multipliers and taking the fractional part; the three individual MLCGs have modulus 30269, 30307 and 30323 and multipliers 171, 172 and 170 respectively [9]. L' Ecuyer combines several left shift register generators (LFSR) by adding their outputs bitwise modulo 2 [10, 11].

F. Inversive Congruential Generator

Eichenauer and Lehn introduced the Inversive Congruential Generators (ICG) in 1986. These generators use the modular multiplicative inverse to generate the next number in a sequence.

The Inversive Congruential Generator is given by the following recurrence:

$$x \equiv ax_{i-1}^- + c \pmod{p} \quad (8)$$

Where x^- is the multiplicative inverse of x modulo m , if it is existed, otherwise it is equal to zero, and its defined as follows:

$1 \equiv x^-x \pmod{m}$. Niederreiter in [12] and Eichenauer, Grothe, and Lehn in [13] show that the inversive congruential generators have good uniformity properties.

In 1994, Eichenauer-Herrmann and Ickstadt proposed the explicit inversive congruential generator, this produces odd integers between 0 and $m-1$. In 1996, a modification was suggested by Eichenauer-Herrmann, which produces all the non-integers up to $m-1$, the generator is given by:

$$x_i \equiv i[(ai+b)^-] \pmod{2^p}, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (9)$$

where $a \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, $b \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, and $p \geq 4$, the period of such generator is m .

The main advantage of inversive congruential generators over linear congruential generators is that tuples made from Inversive Congruential Generator do not fall in hyper-planes, however the computation of modular inversion is costly.

G. Counter Based Random Number Generators

Counter-based random number generators (CBRNGs) obtain the n^{th} random number can by applying bijection keyed function b on: $x_n = b_k(n)$, where b can be a cryptographic block ciphers and n is a p -bit integer counter.

A family of CBRNGs is as follows :

$f : S \rightarrow S$ is the transition function

$g : K \times Z_J \times S \rightarrow U$ is the output function.

In the function g , ' k ' is a member of the key space K , the index, $j \in Z_J$ is used to extract a small number, J of output values from each internal state of the PRNG. The output function is composition of a simple selector h_j , and a complex keyed bijection b_k : $g_{k,j} = h_j \circ b_k$. The transition function, f is a counter: $f(s) = (s+1) \bmod 2^p$, The period of counter base PRNG is $j2^p$ [14].

The first family of counter-based PRNGs is based on Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and threefish block cipher. High-performance CPUs from Intel and AMD have supported the AES-NI instructions that improve the performance of an AES PRNG. Threefish-256 is much faster than AES on platforms that do not support the AES-NI instructions. The next family is based on modifying a cryptographic block cipher by reducing the number of rounds, and simplify the key schedule, called ARS, Threefry. On CPUs with AES-NI support, ARS has outstanding performance as a PRNG. It is faster than any other PRNG conventional or counter-based on CPUs with AES-NI support.

The last counter-based PRNGs is Philox that uses multiply instruction to scramble the bits :

$$\text{mulhi}(a, b) = \lfloor (a \times b) / 2^W \rfloor$$

$$\text{mullo}(a, b) = (a \times b) \bmod 2^W,$$

The Philox S-box is a Feistel function that takes two words (L, R) out of a block of N words of w bits and computes

$$\hat{L} = \text{mullo}(R, M)$$

$$\hat{R} = \text{mulhi}(R, M) \oplus k \oplus L$$

When $N = 2$, the Philox-2xW-R bijection performs R rounds of the Philox S-box on a pair of W -bit inputs. When N is larger, the inputs are permuted using the Threefish N -word P-box before being fed into $N/2$ Philox S-boxes, each with its own multiplier M , and key k . The $N/2$ multipliers are constant, while the $N/2$ keys are updated for each round based on Weyl sequence [14].

H. Cryptographic Pseudo-random Number Generator

The minimum requirement to consider a pseudo-random generator as a secure one is to have the length l of the random seed sufficiently large, in such a way that an adversary cannot search all 2^l elements in order to relive the key (seed). The output sequence of pseudo-random number generator

should be indistinguishable from truly random sequences and unpredictable.

PRBGs pass all poly-time statistical tests, if no poly-time algorithm can distinguish between an output sequence of the generator and a truly random sequence with probability significantly greater than 1/2. Where, PRBGs pass the next bit test if there is no poly-time algorithm can predict the $(r + 1)$ bit of a given sequence s with probability significantly greater than 1/2 [15].

Definition II.2. A pseudo-random generator is asymptotically secure if it passes all polynomial time statistical tests with tolerance negligible in n [15].

Theorem II.1. A PRBG passes the next-bit test if and only if it passes all poly-time statistical tests.

If a PRBG passes the next-bit test, then it is called a cryptographically secure pseudo-random bit generator (CSPRNG). Such generators can be obtained from an arbitrary one-way function.

Definition II.3. A function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a one-way function if $f(x)$ is easy to compute for all $x \in X$, but for all elements y , it is computationally infeasible to find $x \in X$ such that $f(x) = y$ [1].

One-way functions can be used to generate pseudo-random sequences by picking a random seed s then applying the function to the sequence $\langle sn \rangle$. Examples of one-way functions are cryptographic hash function such as SHA-1, and a block cipher such as Data Encryption Standard (DES).

Definition II.4. Let f be a function with domain $\{0, 1\}^*$ and define the function f_n to be the restriction of f to the domain $\{0, 1\}^n$ (i.e., for every $x \in \{0, 1\}^n$, $f_n(x) = f(x)$). Then a one-way function f is called a one-way permutation if for every n , the function f_n is 1-1 and onto $\{0, 1\}^n$.

In one-way permutations, any value y uniquely determines its pre-image x , since a permutation f is a bijection. Thus, even though y fully determines x , it is still hard to find x in polynomial-time[1].

1) *Ad Hoc Method:* The method of using one-way functions in generate pseudo-random sequences is called ad-hoc methods. Even though it is not proven to be secure, it is appropriate for most applications. Examples of such methods are ANSI X9.17 generator and FIPS 186 generator. ANSI X9.17 generator is used by many applications including financial security schemes and PGP. It is a U.S. Federal Information Processing Standard (FIPS) approved method. It uses Triple DES with two keys to produce random numbers [1].

ANSI X9.17 Pseudo-random Bit Generator Algorithm

Let s be a 64-bit random seed, m be an integer, k be DES E-D-E encryption key, and D a 64-bit representation of time/date

- 1) Compute $I = Ek(D)$

- 2) For $i = 1$ to m do
 $x_i \leftarrow k(I \oplus s)$
 $s \leftarrow Ek(x_i \oplus I)$.
 - 3) Return (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) .
-

FIPS is approved methods for pseudo-randomly generating Digital Signature (DSA) private key k , and DSA per-message secret k . Both algorithms use a randomly generated secret seed s and one-way function constructed by using either SHA-1 or DES.

FIPS186 Algorithm for DSA private keys using SHA-1

Input: an integer m and a 160-bit prime number q

Output: m pseudorandom numbers k_1, \dots, k_m in the interval $[0, q - 1]$

Parameters: $(b, G) = (160, \text{DES})$ or $(b, G) = (160, \text{SHA1})$.

Let s be a secret random seed with b bits, and $t = 160$ bits constant $t = \text{efcdab89 98badcfe 10325476 c3d2e1f0 67452301}$

- 1) For $i=1$ to m do
 $k_i \leftarrow G(t, s) \bmod q$
 $s \leftarrow (1 + s + k_i) \bmod 2^b$
 - 2) Return (k_1, \dots, k_m)
-

2) *Secure Pseudo-random Number Generator:* Blum-Blum-Shub pseudo-random bit generator (BBS) is a Cryptographic Secure Generator under the assumption that integer factorization is infeasible.

Blum-Blum-Shub pseudorandom bit generator Algorithm

- 1) Generate two large secret random (and distinct) primes p and q each congruent to 3 modulo 4
 - 2) Compute $n = pq$.
 - 3) Select a random integer s (seed) between $[1, n - 1]$ such that $\text{gcd}(s, n) = 1$
 - 4) Compute $x_0 \leftarrow s^2 \bmod n$.
 - 5) For $i= 1$ to l do
 - a. $x_i \leftarrow x_{i-1}^2 \bmod n$.
 - b. $z_i \leftarrow$ the least significant bit of x_i .
 - 6) Output sequence z_1, z_2, \dots, z_l .
-

The primes p and q are selected in such a way that factoring $n = pq$ is computationally infeasible. i.e. the computation takes too long time to compute using super computers. Also, in order to pass the elliptic curve factoring algorithm p and q should be sufficiently large and have the same length of bit. The efficiency of the generator can be improved by extracting the j least significant bits of x_i in step b in the above algorithm instead of extracting the only one bit, where

$j = c \lg \lg n$ and c is a constant [1].

The RSA pseudorandom bit generator is another CSPRNG assuming that the RSA problem is intractable. The RSA problem is finding e^{th} roots modulo a composite integer n . The conditions on the parameters n and e ensure that for each integer $c \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$ there is exactly one $m \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$ such that $m^e \equiv c \pmod{n}$. Therefore, the function $f : Z_n \rightarrow Z_n$ is defined as $f(m) = m^e \pmod{n}$ is a permutation [1].

RSA Pseudorandom Bit Generator Algorithm

- 1) Generate two secret prime p and q
 - 2) Compute $n = pq$, and $\phi = (p-1)(q-1)$.
 - 3) Select a random integer e , $1 < e < \phi$, such that $\gcd(e, \phi) = 1$.
 - 4) Select a random integer x_0 (the seed) between $[1, n-1]$.
 - 5) For $i = 1$ to l do
 - a. $x_i \leftarrow x_{i-1}^e \pmod{n}$.
 - b. $z_i \leftarrow$ the least significant bit of x_i .
 - 6) Output the sequence z_1, z_2, \dots, z_l .
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III. QUASI-RANDOM NUMBERS

Quasi-random numbers are highly uniform deterministic sequences with small star discrepancy and called low discrepancy sequences.

Definition III.1. For P_N points x_1, \dots, x_N in the s -dimensional half-open unit cube $I^s = [0, 1)^s$, $s \geq 1$, and a subinterval J of I^s we put:

$$g(J; P_N) = 1/N |P_N \cap J| - V(J)$$

where $|A|$ is the number of n , $1 \leq n \leq N$, with $x_n \in J$ and $V(J)$ is the volume of J . Then the star discrepancy of the points P_N is defined as:

$$D_\infty^*(P_N) = \sup_{j(x) \in J^*} |g(J(x), P_N)|$$

Different kinds of discrepancy can be defined by restricting J to a certain class of sets and taking a norm of $g(J, P_N)$ over this class [17]. L_2 -star-discrepancy is another type of discrepancy define as

$$D_2^*(P_N) = \left\{ \int_{[0,1]^s} [g(J(x), P_N)]^2 dx \right\}^{1/2}$$

The star discrepancy of the low-discrepancy sequences, infinite sequences, is order of $ON^{-1} \log N^s$. Examples of such sequences are the Halton sequence [18], Sobol' sequence [19], Faure sequence [20], Niederreiter sequences [6], and Niederreiter-Xing sequences [21].

A. Halton Sequences

Halton sequence was introduced in 1960 by Halton for constructing point sets of arbitrary length [18]. The sequence

is a generalization of one-dimensional van der Corput sequence. Halton sequence is defined based on the radical inverse function as follows:

$$Q_P(n) = \frac{a_0}{p} + \frac{a_1}{p^2} + \dots + \frac{a_m}{p^{m+1}}$$

where p is a prime number, and the digital expansion of n in base p is defined as $n = a_0 + a_1p + \dots + a_m p^m$, with integers $0 \leq a_j < p$. The Halton sequence, X_n , in s -dimensions is then defined as

$$X_n = (Q_{P_1}(n), Q_{P_2}(n), \dots, Q_{P_s}(n))$$

where the dimensional bases p_1, p_2, \dots, p_s are the first s primes sorted in increasing order. One of the advantages of Halton sequence over the other low-discrepancy sequences is that the Halton sequence is much easier to implement due to the ease of implementation of the radical inverse function [22].

B. Faure sequences

The Faure sequence is a permutation of the Halton sequence. It uses only one base for all dimensions, and the base is the smallest prime that is larger than or equal to the number of dimensions.

Let $s \geq 1$ and p be a prim number greater than s . For $x = \frac{a_0}{p} + \frac{a_1}{p^2} + \dots + \frac{a_k}{p^{k+1}}$ and define

$$C_P(x) = \frac{b_0}{p} + \frac{b_1}{p^2} + \dots + \frac{b_k}{p^{k+1}}$$

where $b_j = \sum_{i=j}^k \frac{i!}{j!(i-j)!} a_i \pmod{p}$. We define the sequence ξ over $[0, 1)^s$ as

$$\xi = (Q_P(n), C_P(Q_P(n)), \dots, C_P^{s-1}(Q_P(n))) \quad (10)$$

with $Q_P(n) = \frac{a_0}{p} + \frac{a_1}{p^2} + \dots + \frac{a_j}{p^{j+1}}$ define from the digital expansion of n in base p , $n = a_0 + a_1p + \dots + a_j p^j$ [23]

C. Sobol' Sequences

The Sobol' sequence is generated from a set of binary vectors v_i^j of length w bits, v_i^j , $i = 1, 2, \dots, w$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, d$. v_i^j are called direction numbers. For dimension j these direction numbers are generated using a primitive polynomial over the finite field F_2 with elements $0, 1$ [24].

Let $p_j(x) = x^q + a_1 x^{q-1} + \dots + a_{q-1} x + 1$ be the primitive polynomial used in generating dimension j of the Sobol' sequence, we use the polynomial coefficients to define a recurrence for calculating v_i^j as follows:

$$v_i^j = a_1 v_{i-1}^j \oplus a_2 v_{i-2}^j \oplus \dots \oplus a_{q-1} v_{i-q+1}^j \oplus v_{i-q}^j \oplus (v_{i-q}^j / 2^q) \quad (11)$$

where $i > q$, \oplus denotes the bitwise XOR operation, and the last term is v_{i-q}^j shifted right q places. The initial numbers $v_1^j \cdot 2^w, v_2^j \cdot 2^w, \dots, v_q^j \cdot 2^w$ can be arbitrary odd integers smaller than $2, 2^2, \dots$, and 2^q , respectively. A different primitive polynomial should be used to generate Sobol sequence in

each dimension.

Let the binary expansion of nonnegative integer n be given by $n = b_1 2^0 + b_2 2^1 + \dots + b_w 2^{w-1}$, then the Sobol' sequence x_n^j in dimension j is generated by

$$x_n^j = b_1 v_1^j \oplus b_2 v_2^j \oplus \dots \oplus b_w v_w^j \quad (12)$$

Generating the Sobol' sequence as defined in equation (12) is time consuming, an efficient way to generate the Sobol' sequence is given by Antonov and Saleev [25] as follows:

$$x_n^j = g_1 v_1^j \oplus g_2 v_2^j \oplus \dots \oplus g_w v_w^j \quad (13)$$

where $\dots g_1 g_2 g_3$ is the Gray code representation of n , which can be obtained from the binary representation of n as follows: $\dots g_3 g_2 g_1 = \dots b_3 b_2 b_1 \oplus \dots b_4 b_3 b_2$.

The Gray code for n and the Gray code for $n + 1$ differ only in the digit relative to the rightmost zero in the binary representation of n . Using these properties, and defining x_n^j by equation (13), we can calculate x_{n+1}^j in terms of x_n^j as $x_{n+1}^j = x_n^j \oplus v_c^j$, where v_c^j is the direction number associated with the right most zero in the binary representation of x_n^j .

D. (t, m, s) Nets, and (t, s) Sequences

to give a definition of the (t, m, s) net, we need to introduce the concept of digital nets in its general form, which is over a finite ring R .

Definition III.2. let $s \geq 1$ and $k \geq 1$ be integers. Choose

- 1) A commutative ring R with identity and cardinality b (usually \mathbb{Z}_b);
- 2) bijections $\psi_r : \mathbb{Z}_b \rightarrow R$ for $0 \leq r \leq k - 1$;
- 3) bijections $\eta_{jl} : R \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_b$ for $1 \leq j \leq s$ and $1 \leq l \leq k$;
- 4) generating matrices C^1, \dots, C^s of dimension $\infty \times k$ over R .

For $i = 0, \dots, b^k - 1$ let $i = \sum_{r=0}^{k-1} a_r b^r$ with $a_r \in \mathbb{Z}_b$, be the digit expansion of I in base b . Consider the vector

$$y = (\psi_0(a_0), \dots, \psi_{k-1}(a_{k-1}))^T \in R^k$$

and compute $(b_{j,1}, b_{j,2}, \dots)^T = C^j \cdot y$, where each element $b_{j,l}$ is in R . For $j = 1, \dots, s$. let

$$\eta_{ij} = \frac{n_{i1} b_{j1}}{b} + \frac{n_{i2} b_{j2}}{b^2} + \dots$$

then $P_n = \{u_i = (u_{i1}, \dots, u_{is}), i = 0, \dots, n - 1\}$ with $n = b^k$ is a digital net over R in base b .

Now, we can introduce the definition of the (t, m, s) net in Niederreiter. An elementary interval of $[0, 1]^s$ in base b is a set of the form $E = \prod_{j=1}^s [\frac{t_j}{b^{k_j}}, \frac{t_j+1}{b^{k_j}})$ where b, t_i, k_i are nonnegative integers with $b \geq 2$, and $t_i \leq b^{k_j}$.

Definition III.3. Let t and m be nonnegative integers. A finite sequence $X_1, \dots, X_n \in [0, 1]^s$ with $n = b^m$ is a (t, m, s) -net in base b if every elementary interval of volume b^{t-m} contains exactly b^t points of the sequence [26].

Smaller values of t imply better equidistribution properties for the net. For the best case, with $t = 0$, every elementary

interval of volume $1/n$ has one of the n points in the sequence [27].

Definition III.4. Let t be a nonnegative integer. An infinite sequence $X_1, X_2, \dots \in [0, 1]^s$ is a (t, s) -sequence in base b if for all $m \geq 0$ and all $k \geq 0$ the finite sequence $X_{kb^m+1}, \dots, X_{(k+1)b^m}$ is a (t, m, s) -net in base b .

IV. TESTING RANDOM NUMBER GENERATORS

A set of statistical tests have been developed to measure the quality of random bit generators, these tests detect certain kinds of weaknesses that generators might have. The most common testing suites software are TestU01, DIEHARD, SPRNG, and NIST.

RNG tests can be divided into two kinds: empirical tests and theoretical tests. Empirical tests are applied to sequences produce by a random number generator to evaluate certain statistics. Theoretical tests consider the recurrence that defines the generator and employ mathematical techniques to understand its prosperities; spectral test is an example of theoretical test [28]. This section considers only the empirical tests. Chi-square test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test are used as a based on the empirical tests. Each empirical test takes a sample output sequence and probabilistically determines whether it prosperities look like a truly random sequence or not; based on that, generators may be rejected or accepted.

Empirical tests are applied to a sequence produced by PRG to investigate their randomness, we define the sequences used by these tests as follows: $\langle U_n \rangle$ refers to a sequence of real number between zero and 1, where $\langle Y_n \rangle$ refers to a sequence of integer number between zero and $d - 1$ using $Y_n = \lfloor dU_n \rfloor$.

A. Equidistribution Test (Frequency Test)

The Frequency test goal is to determine whether numbers in a given sequence are uniformly distributed between zero and one. There are two ways to do the test, the first way uses the sequence $\langle U_n \rangle$ and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with $F(x) = x$ for $0 \leq x \leq 1$, where the second way uses the sequence $\langle Y_n \rangle$ and chooses d to be 100 in decimal computer or 64 on binary computer. For every integer r such that $0 \leq r < d$, counts the number of times that $Y_j = r$ for $0 \leq j < n$ then for each integer r applies the Chi-Square test with $k = d$ and probability $p_s = 1/d$ [28].

B. Serial Test (two-bit test)

The test insure that pairs of successive numbers are uniformly distributed in an independent manner. In other words, the test determines whether the number of occurrences of 00, 01, 10, 11 are approximately the same. To carry out the serial test, we count the number of times that the pair $(y_{2j}, y_{2j+1}) = (q, r)$ occurs for $0 \leq j < n$, these counts are made for each pair of integer (q, r) with $0 \leq q, r < d$, and the chi-square is applied to $k = d^2$ categories with probability $1/d^2$ in each category [28].

C. Poker Test

Poker test goal is to determine whether sequences of length m each appear approximately the same number of times. The test considers n groups of five successive integers and observes if these groups match the following patterns:

- All different : abcde
- One pair: aabcd
- Two pair: aabbc
- Three of a kind: aaabc
- Full house aaabb
- Four of a kind: aaaab
- Five of a kind: aaaaa

A chi-square test is applied on the number of quintuples in each category. A simpler version is to count the number of distinct values in the set of five, and we would have five categories:

- 5 values = all different
- 4 values = one pair
- 3 values = two pairs, or three of a kind
- 2 values = full house, or four of a kind
- 1 value = five of a kind

Generally, we can consider n groups of k successive numbers and count the number of k - tuples with r different values using the following probability:

$$P_r = \frac{d(d-1)\dots(d-r+1)}{d^k} \binom{nk}{r}, \text{ with } d \text{ number of categories then apply chi-square test [28].}$$

D. Gap Test

Given a sequence $\langle U_n \rangle$, the test examines the length of the gap between occurrence of U_j in a certain range. Let α and β be two real number such that $0 \leq \alpha < \beta \leq 1$, we examine the length of consecutive subsequences $U_j, U_{j+1}, \dots, U_{j+r}, U_{j+(r+1)}$ such that U_j and $U_{j+(r+1)}$ are between α and β but the other U 's are not ; this is a gap of length r .

Algorithm of counting the number of gaps of length $0, 1, \dots, t - 1$ and the number of gaps of length $\geq t$

- 1) Initialize $j \leftarrow -1, s \leftarrow 0$
 - 2) $r \leftarrow 0$
 - 3) if $(\alpha \leq U_j \leq \beta)$ then $j = j + 1$ else go to 5
 - 4) $r \leftarrow r + 1$, go to 3
 - 5) record the gap length // a gap of length r has been found if $r \geq t, Count[t] \leftarrow Count[t] + 1$ else $Count[r] \leftarrow Count[r] + 1$
 - 6) repeat until n gaps are found
-

The chi-square test is performed on the result $(Count[0], Count[1], \dots, Count[t])$ using different length of gaps as the categories and the probability is $P_0 = P, P_1 = P(1-P), P^2 = P(1-P)^2, \dots, P_t = P(1-P)^t$

, where $P = \alpha - \beta$, which is the probability that U_j is between α and β [28].

E. Runs Test

The test goal is to determine whether the number of runs of various length is as expected for a random sequence. Given a sequence, The test gathers the lengths of all increasing or all decreasing subsequences, counts how many there are of each length and computes a revised chi-square statistic [28, p. 67] based on these counts. We cannot directly applied chi-square test to the run counts because of lack of independence, since a long run will tend to be followed by short one. After determining the run lengths we compute:

$$V = \frac{1}{n-6} \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq 6} (count[i] - nb_i)(count[j] - nb_j) a_{ij}$$

where n is the length of the sequence, the matrices of coefficient $A = (a_{ij})_{1 \leq i, j \leq 6}$ and $B = (b_{ij})_{1 \leq i \leq 6}$ are given by

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 4529.4 & 9044.9 & 13568 & 18091 & 22615 & 27892 \\ 9044.9 & 18097 & 27139 & 36187 & 45234 & 55789 \\ 13568 & 27139 & 40721 & 54281 & 67852 & 83685 \\ 18091 & 36187 & 54281 & 72414 & 90470 & 111580 \\ 22615 & 45234 & 67852 & 90470 & 113262 & 139476 \\ 27892 & 55789 & 83685 & 111580 & 139476 & 172860 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} 1/6 \\ 5/24 \\ 11/120 \\ 19/720 \\ 29/5040 \\ 1/840 \end{pmatrix}$$

The statistic V should have the chi-square distribution with 6 degree of freedom , when n is large [28].

F. Permutation Test

The test divides the input sequence into n groups of t elements, the elements in each group can have $t!$ possible relative orderings. The number of times each ordering appears is counted and chi-square test is applied with $k = t!$ with probability $1/t!$ for each ordering [28].

G. Serial Correlation Test

Considering the two observations $(u_0, u_1, \dots, u_{n-1})$ and $(u_1, \dots, u_{n-1}, u_0)$, the serial correlation tests the correlation between these two tuples using the following formula

$$C = \frac{n(u_0 u_1 + u_1 u_2 + \dots + u_{n-2} u_{n-1} + u_{n-1} u_0) - (u_0 + u_1 + \dots + u_{n-1})^2}{n(u_0^2 + u_1^2 + \dots + u_{n-1}^2) - (u_0 + u_1 + \dots + u_{n-1})^2}$$

A good value of C will be between $\mu_n - 2\sigma_n$ and $\mu_n + 2\sigma_n$ where

$$\mu_n = \frac{-1}{n-1}, \sigma_n^2 = \frac{n^2}{(n-1)^2(n-2)}, n > 2$$

V. CONCLUSION

Generating pseudorandom numbers is a prerequisite for many areas including Monte Carlo simulation. This paper survey pseudorandom numbers generators including the linear congruential generator which is one of the well-known pseudorandom numbers generators based on a simple form of recurrences. Te paper also covers the cryptographic secure random number generators and quasi-random numbers. Finlay, the paper presents away to measure the quality of random bit generators using empirical test. The most common testing suites software are TestU01, DIEHARD, SPRNG, and NIST.

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